

Table S9. Multivariate mixed effects logistic regression for *dhfr* and *dhps* gene mutations in pregnant women sampled at ANC booking and the GP (pure mutants versus wild type/mixed)

Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI and *p* values are presented (*p* values <0.05 in bold).

<i>dhfr</i> Fixed effect(s)	N51				C59				S108				triple <i>dhfr</i>			
	OR	[95% CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Age	0.80	0.57	1.13	0.213	0.91	0.64	1.29	0.603	0.92	0.65	1.31	0.656	0.81	0.57	1.15	0.237
Season#	1.18	0.78	1.77	0.430	1.15	0.76	1.74	0.511	1.21	0.80	1.83	0.361	1.30	0.86	1.96	0.216
Visit*	1.24	0.85	1.81	0.254	1.12	0.76	1.64	0.566	1.03	0.71	1.51	0.857	1.17	0.80	1.72	0.409
VisitXage	1.42	0.98	2.06	0.062	1.15	0.79	1.67	0.472	1.08	0.75	1.56	0.685	1.46	1.00	2.12	0.050
- Age in GP samples	1.14	1.00	1.30	0.046	1.05	0.92	1.19	0.511	1.00	0.88	1.14	0.971	1.18	1.03	1.34	0.014

<i>dhps</i> Fixed effect(s)	S436				A437			
	OR	[95% CI]		<i>p</i>	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Age	1.24	0.87	1.75	0.231	0.91	0.63	1.31	0.626
Season#	1.47	0.97	2.24	0.069	0.76	0.49	1.19	0.228
Visit*	0.93	0.64	1.35	0.690	0.76	0.50	1.15	0.198
VisitXage	0.82	0.56	1.18	0.286	1.32	0.89	1.96	0.161
- Age in GP samples	1.01	0.89	1.15	0.863	1.21	1.05	1.40	0.010

#dry season = 0, rainy season = 1; *ANC booking = 0, GP = 1; age centred at 25 years